

NEWS Tool For Timely Detection and Management of Septic Neutropenic Oncology Patients

Colette Spencer, DNP, RN, ACNP-BC, Catherine Cummins, MD, RN, and Melissa Dyo, PhD, RN

Background

- Neutropenic sepsis, as a result of intensive cytotoxic chemotherapy due to hematologic and solid tumor malignancies carries a high mortality of up to 50%.
- The Surviving Sepsis Campaign proposed a 3 hour window for the initial treatment of sepsis and the use of early screening tools.
- Of vital importance is the timely administration of IV fluids and broad spectrum antibiotics within one hour.

Aim

To improve the management of neutropenic septic oncology patients at a tertiary care medical center in the Western United States.

Purpose

Determine the efficacy of the NEWS Tool by comparing time to treatment, ICU transfers, and mortality in septic oncology patients before the NEWS and after.

NEWS Tool

Physiological Parameters	3	2	1	0	1	2	3
Temp (°C)	< 35		35 - 36	36.1 - 38	38.1 - 39	> 39	
Pulse (bpm)	< 41		41 - 50	51 - 90	91 - 110	111 - 130	> 130
Resp (bpm)	< 8		9 - 11	12 - 20		21 - 24	> 24
SBP (mmHg)	< 90	91 - 100	101 - 110	111 - 220			> 220
SO ₂	< 92%	92v- 93%	94 - 95%	> 96%			
Oxygen		YES		NO			

Concern about a patient should lead to escalation, regardless of the score.

Adaptation of the NEWS Tool for the Oncology patient

NEWS Score	Frequency of Monitoring	Clinical Response
0-2 (SIRS: Category 1)	Assess q every four hours	NEWS screen q shift
3-5 (Sepsis: Category 2)	Assess q every two hours	Assess q every two hours
6 ≥ (Severe Sepsis: Category 3)	Assess q every 15 minutes	MAT and activate txt bundle: Blood work, IV bolus(s) (30ml/kg), broad spectrum antibiotics, vs q15 mins)
6 ≥ + SBP < 90 (Septic Shock: Category 4)	Continuous vital sign monitoring	IV fluids and ICU Transfer

Notes: SIRS = systemic inflammatory response, 6 ≥ = six greater than or equal to, q = every, NEWS = National Early Warning Screening, IV = intravenous, ICU = intensive care unit, MAT = medical assessment team, txt = treatment

Methods

- A retrospective chart review
- Sample - oncology patients
- Sampling plan - patients exposed to NEWS or standard care
- Setting – tertiary care hospital in Los Angeles
- 4 phases to the quality improvement project
- A NEWS tool score of 6 > triggered the medical assessment team response and treatment bundle

Results

Demographics

The post-NEWS group was, on average, ten years younger than the comparison group, had fewer patients suffering from HTN or DM2.

Time to Treatment

NEWS score of 6 ≥ reduced the time to treatment in 50% (13) of the post-NEWS group compared to 47% (15) in the pre-NEWS group.

TIME TO TREATMENT

Sepsis Categories

Sepsis was detected at a NEWS score of 6 or > (category 3) and septic shock (category 4).

MORTALITY AND NEWS CATEGORY

4-hour before data

This was clinically significant as it indicates 77% (20) cases of severe sepsis and 15% (4) cases of septic shock were not picked up as having sepsis 4 hour earlier.

Implications for Practice

- NEWS tool picked up late sepsis
- 4-hour before data needs to be incorporated in future studies
- Many errors with paper entries and this is evidence for computerized protocols